

Petrochemical Industry Aerial Robotic Inspection: A Novel Concept for Landing and Deploying Robots on Pipes

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Abstract—This paper introduces a hybrid aerial robot for Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) thickness petrochemical pipes inspection and a novel method for recognizing and landing on pipes in areas where Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) signals are degraded. In these environments, the inspection of pipes at height presents a high risk for the workers. We have addressed the issue of landing safely on pipes by implementing tilted rotors and a force control technique. Due to the type of environment, a LiDAR-Inertial Odometry has been implemented for the aircraft localization. In addition, pipes are detected and tracked using a fusion of some of the onboard sensors: a depth camera and a 2D LiDAR. The outcome is an unmanned aerial vehicle with the capability of deploying a robotic crawler on pipes at height while performing safe landing and takeoff. A demonstration of autonomous landing in an outdoor controlled environment can be found at https://youtu.be/yYRzDUkc_Bk.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progress in the field of robotics has already transformed the inspection sector today, and it is widely expected to revolutionize it with the addition of the latest trends. Among all the technologies that are advancing today, one of the most promising is the deployment of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) or aerial robots and, specifically, those that are capable of conducting contact-based inspections. These allow for a variety of tasks that can be automated, optimized, and conducted securely. There have been two primary methods for this kind of airborne inspection robots: aerial robots that make contact and hybrid robots that navigates along the pipe taking measurements. The first option enables communication during flight [1] and facilitates the usage of this method. Nevertheless, this particular approach is restricted by the duration of the aerial robot's flight (often about 20 minutes). Additionally, this alternative is best suited for expansive structures such as tanks, as it becomes challenging to access intricate and crowded areas using a flying aerial robot.

Contact examination with aerial and hybrid robots consists of three stages: 1) moving from the starting point to the area near the inspection location, making sure to avoid collisions and being able to react quickly if there are unexpected obstacles; 2) getting closer to the intended operating position with greater precision and landing on the pipe that needs to be inspected; and 3) conducting a thorough inspection using a magnetic crawler with ultrasonic sensor for checking the thickness of the metallic pipe. Phases 1) and 2) should take

Fig. 1. Autonomous flight performed during the outdoor controlled experiments.

perception into account to prevent collisions. This includes perception-based localization and accurate Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) in the GNSS-Denied, or partially degraded environments.

Regarding GNSS-Denied localization, a commonly used method is odometry which relies on the combination of Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data and eyesight, without absolute localization [2]. Precise 3D positioning in the global coordinate system and mapping can be achieved by using various sensor-based methods such as Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR), stereo cameras, or radio range measurements concerning beacons. When the robot is many meters away from objects, a 3D LiDAR offers improved precision and dependability. Ultimately, for short distances, stereo cameras can be used to combine the point clouds generated by the camera with those produced by the 3D LiDAR.

In addition to localization, planning is another essential aspect of autonomous navigation. The top level in the planning of aerial robots is mission planning, which in this case refers to the inspection plan. The next step involves organizing the specific tasks necessary to carry out the inspection plan that was previously developed. In [3], task and motion planning are combined in a method that checks the geometric constraints involved in the symbolic actions and modifies the plan until the geometric constraints are met. This involves creating and managing a geometric representation of the symbolic plan to make sure that the current geometric condition aligns with the current symbolic condition. Traditional motion planning techniques, such as Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT), have been expanded to take into account kinematic and dynamic limitations [4], or even the control system [5], which are especially beneficial

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in aerial manipulation.

However, aerial robots frequently experience disturbances such as unaccounted aerodynamic effects, imprecise placement, and other factors. This is especially accurate for tiny outdoor aerial robots where the wind has a notable impact. In addition, it is extremely challenging to take into account all the unforeseen items and forces that may be engaged in the contact examination. Next, responsiveness is required to enhance the safety of the airborne robots. Autonomous responsiveness should rely on perceptual abilities, namely incorporating range sensors, computer vision, and force/torque sensors. Further information on the perception and planning capabilities in aerial robotic manipulation can be found in reference [6].

This work presents the software and hardware of a hybrid robot with the capability of navigating and landing autonomously in pipes in GNSS-denied environments, as shown in Fig. 1. In addition, it can deploy and collect inspection crawlers on the same pipeline.

The rest of the manuscript is structured as follows: In Section II, the aerial platform is presented at the hardware level. The crawler deployment and collection mechanism, the landing gear and the sensor setup that will allow autonomous tasks to be carried out will be presented. Section III presents the software architecture of the aerial robot, the flight manager, the perception algorithms and the control structure. After that, Section IV presents a series of results and evaluations of the autonomous algorithms. Finally, in Section V a series of conclusions will be presented.

II. AERIAL PLATFORM

The hybrid aerial robot under consideration is designed as a multicopter, featuring a distinctive configuration with six tilted rotors.

Conventional multicopters, reliant on roll and pitch rotations for spatial navigation, encounter notable challenges when trying to land on pipes. If the aircraft experiences any disruption, it must counteract it by adjusting its roll and pitch, making landing difficult. Factors such as wind or the pipe itself can induce unintended rotations, complicating the landing process and making it very risky in special situations. In contrast, tilted multicopters can be purposefully designed to execute lateral movements while maintaining a horizontal orientation throughout the flight. This design characteristic offers a distinct advantage over conventional counterparts, enabling more precise control during landings on challenging surfaces like pipes. A comparison between the behaviour of this two types of multicopters is shown in Fig. 2.

The design of this aircraft is purpose-built for precision landings on cylindrical structures, particularly pipes. It features six rotor units strategically positioned at specific angles along an elongated body. The landing gear is characterized by its ergonomic design and interchangeability, facilitating adaptation to a diverse range of pipe diameters.

The aircraft is equipped with an advanced navigation sensor suite comprising a 3D LiDAR, a 2D LiDAR, and a depth camera. Employing sophisticated algorithms, this

Fig. 2. Comparison of pipe landing behavior between tilted and standard multicopters.

sensor suite ensures the generation of precise positional data for the UAV within its relative environment.

1) *Landing gear*: The landing gear is engineered to facilitate seamless interactions with cylindrical structures, notably pipes. Its distinct V-shaped frame serves as a guiding mechanism during descent, ensuring precise alignment with the target pipe for a secure and successful landing. This geometric configuration not only aids in maneuvering the UAV along the descent trajectory but also guarantees optimal alignment with the pipe surface, mitigating the risk of misalignment or instability upon touchdown.

Fig. 3. Landing Gear of the Aerial Robot. (Left: UAV landed on real pipe; Right: Zoom to the gripper)

Furthermore, the landing gear incorporates four linear actuators, each one calibrated to facilitate and ensure secure locking of the UAV onto the pipe upon landing. These actuators act as pivotal components in anchoring the UAV to the pipe surface, thereby enhancing stability and ensuring robust adherence to the pipe.

This v-shape guides the UAV along the descent procedure and aligns the UAV with the pipe ensuring a complete, safe and successful landing. Moreover it contains four linear actuators to lock the UAV to the pipe once landed. The aerial robot landed on the pipeline and with the linear actuators locked is shown in Fig. 3.

2) *Crawler deployment & recover*: Features a linear actuator with a hook-shaped terminus, designed for efficient attachment and detachment of crawlers. This mechanism streamlines the deployment process, offering swift and reliable engagement. Thanks to this linear actuator it is possible to deploy the crawler in the gallery to carry out the necessary measurements and to pull it out to recover it after the inspection has been carried out. This system is illustrated in Fig. 4.

3) *Perception sensor suite*: In order to navigate safely and autonomously in a large GNSS-denied environment and to be

Fig. 4. Crawler Deployment & Rescue System. (Left: Real deployment of the crawler. Right: CAD design of the crawler system)

able to detect the pipeline with a high degree of accuracy, the following sensor suite has been selected.

For the autonomous navigation, an Ouster OS1 has been selected. Thanks to its high accuracy and the algorithm proposed in Section III-A2, autonomous and safe navigation is achieved. The 3D LiDAR has been integrated into the front area of the aircraft. This placement allows for a minimum 180-degree field of view (FOV) with the entire vertical FOV available for autonomous flights. This is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. CAD model of the HYBRID Perception Sensors Suite.

For the detection of pipes in the aircraft reference frame, sensor fusion using data from two different types of sensors has been carried out: a depth camera, so that a three-dimensional view of the target pipe can be obtained; and a 2D LiDAR, which allows the section of the pipe to be known with great precision and helps to deal with the errors of the depth sensor. Fig. 6 shows how the minimum detection range of the sensors has been made to coincide with the base of the aircraft. This allows the pipeline to be accurately detected even when landed on it.

Fig. 6. Pipe Detection Sensors FOVs. (left: Realsense D435i; right: Hokuyo UST-10LX).

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

One of the main objectives is the development of a fully autonomous and safe aerial vehicle. To accomplish this task it is necessary to develop a complete system based on the following modules. An overview of the software architecture of the aerial robot is shown in Fig. 7.

The perception module is in charge of, besides guaranteeing the localization in GNSS-denied environments, being able to work with global landing references and detect the pipe to be landed using the onboard sensors. The control module designed for this aircraft includes a force control mode that allows flying horizontally and prevents the UAV from flipping when it comes into contact with the pipe during landing and takeoff.

Finally, the flight manager module is in charge of manage the autonomous flight status of the aircraft as well as generate the references to land on the target pipeline to be inspected.

Fig. 7. Aerial Robot Software Architecture Diagram.

A. Multi-sensor perception

The perception module is responsible for providing the aerial robot an environmental awareness. It contains three different staggered layers and each one is in charge of generating a transform between coordinate systems; A global localization layer (T_{GL}), a relative localization layer (T_{LD}) and a pipeline detection and mapping layer (T_{DP}). Fig. 8 illustrates a diagram of the transformations tree of the aerial robot.

Fig. 8. Diagram of the transformations between different coordinates systems.

1) *Global Localization*: The global localization algorithm is based on DLL [7]. This method takes as input a pre-existing map of the surroundings, an initial guess of the position of the robot in the map, the LiDAR point cloud and current IMU information of the robot. As a result, an estimate of the robot's position and orientation on the map is generated, in other words, the transformation T_{GL} .

It is necessary to perform pre-processing on the map, which involves creating a three-dimensional grid of the same size as the map. At each vertex of the grid, the shortest distance to a specific point in the point cloud must be determined. Therefore, upon receiving the point cloud from the LiDAR, the algorithm applies a trilinear interpolation operation to each point using the pre-computed map. This computation is executed due to the fact that for every point incorporated into the grid, there are eight adjacent vertices to the corresponding subcube. In order to optimize these distances for the purpose of repeating the operation, the global localization algorithm employs a nonlinear optimizer until a local minimum is achieved.

The nonlinear optimizer carries a significant risk of producing an invalid local minimum; therefore, the initial approximation that is fed into the algorithm is critical. While absolute precision is not a prerequisite for this estimation, it is advisable to approximate it in order to facilitate convergence.

Repeatability of the system can be achieved thanks to this prior map, which may have been previously generated from a digital twin or during the inspection work. An inspection operator is able to select the landing zone on the map and generate control references to that zone.

2) *Relative Localization*: The relative localization algorithm is responsible for generating the odometry data at a high frequency, which represents the movement of the UAV between its take-off location and its current position. In other words, it produces the transformation T_{LD} at high frequency to be able to navigate safely in the GNSS-Denied environment.

This algorithm is based on LIO-SAM [8]. The architecture works by establishing a tightly coupled fusion between the LiDAR and the IMU, this architecture generates a factor graph that integrates and optimizes the sensor measurements for the construction of the map. A pre-integration of the IMU is also used to obtain an initial guess on the displacement estimation, by integrating angular velocities and linear accelerations. Due to the significant drift introduced by the double integration of an IMU, the architecture suggests employing short-term integration to rectify the IMU's bias. This is achieved through registration of LiDAR point cloud information within the constructed map at lower frequencies. For the algorithm to operate in real time, LiDAR readings that fail to observe an adequate displacement relative to the preceding reading (referred to as LiDAR keyframes) are discarded. A substantial amount of superfluous data that would otherwise impede computation is eliminated in this manner. The IMU readings are incorporated between LiDAR keyframes, resulting in their convergence at a node of the graph representing the current state of the location at a

specific instant.

3) *Pipes Detection & Tracking*: The goal of this module is compute the transformation T_{DP} as robustly as possible. In this component the merging of two independent pipe detectors shall be performed. One from the point cloud of the depth camera and the other from the 2D laser. These detections shall be made in the sensor reference frame, and then, through the transform calculated with the estimated relative location, shall be converted to the odometry reference frame. This allows merging different measurements over time independently of the aircraft position, otherwise we would only be dealing with local estimations. A diagram of this pipe detector is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Relative Pipe Detection Diagram.

The depth camera point cloud pipe detection algorithm is mainly based on the one proposed at [9].

The laser pipe detection algorithm uses the measurements of the 2D LiDAR, which is placed perpendicular to the pipes to be detected. As in the case of the point cloud, the algorithm consists of two stages: a first preprocessing stage and a second stage of pipeline estimation. In the first phase, an Euclidean clustering is also performed to obtain the subsets of points that could be a section of the pipeline. Once these sets of points of pipe sections are obtained, a circle fitting is performed using a least squares method for each point, $P_i = (x_i, y_i)$ of each cluster, as is shown in Eq. 1.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A \\ B \\ C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_i x_i^2 & \sum_i x_i y_i & \sum_i x_i \\ \sum_i x_i y_i & \sum_i y_i^2 & \sum_i y_i \\ \sum_i x_i & \sum_i y_i & \sum_i 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -\sum_i (x_i^3 + x_i y_i^2) \\ -\sum_i (x_i^2 y_i + y_i^3) \\ -\sum_i (x_i^2 + y_i^2) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = -2a; \quad B = -2b; \quad C = a^2 + b^2 - r^2 \quad (1)$$

Where (a, b) and r are the center position and the radius of the estimated circle, respectively.

Finally, the objective of the pipe global database is to track the global frame of each estimated pipeline and to perform a fusion of the observations made by each sensor. In this way, it is possible to work with different types of data such as the estimation of the cylinder made by RANSAC and the estimation of the pipe section made by means of the least squares method. In general, the operation of this module is as follows: Each time a new observation arrives, regardless of which sensor, it is evaluated whether it is associated to a pipe already existing in the database or it is necessary to create a new instance. In the case where a new instance should be created, a Kalman Filter is created with a static motion

Fig. 10. Tilted Control Diagram Overview.

model to filter and merge the measurements made. In the case where the observation corresponds to a pipe already existing in the database, a fusion between the observation and the Kalman Filter estimate is performed to calculate the new pipe dimension and the filter is updated. This allows to estimate the pipe dimensions, such as its radius and length, to calculate its position in the global frame.

B. Tilted Control

The decision to use a design with tilted rotors have been developed due to the nature of the mission itself. Landing on a pipe is a high risk operation because the interaction with the structure could destabilize the UAV leading to potential accidents. However, employing lateral forces for flying, the UAV can maintain a stable and flat position offering a significant advantage during approaches and landings on pipelines.

Primarily, flying with lateral forces guarantees the UAV is horizontal during the landing, minimizing the risk for tipping upon UAV disarming. Secondly, alignment with the pipe becomes more direct, reducing the process to a point-to-point displacement characterized by neutral attitude and a single yaw rotation. Last, operating in a stage with a high density of obstacles, such as a refinery, becomes safer avoiding abrupt attitude changes.

This advantages of using tilted rotors affects however, to the capacity of handling external disturbances owing to the constrained acceleration capacity along the XY axes and increases the complexity of the dynamic model essential for characterizing the allocation matrix. Moreover, attaining flight proficiency in this mode requires a very precise low-level control to keep the UAV with zero roll and pitch. In this context, it is important to highlight that the choice of rotor tilt angles has been determined based on dynamic considerations ensuring the UAV exhibits adequate response characteristics

to guarantee maneuverability and controllability, thereby ensuring safe flight operations.

In Fig. 10 is shown the control architecture. On it, three fundamental blocks can be discerned:

1) *Attitude control (yellow block)*: It adheres to the architecture commonly referred as cascade control. In this context three proportional (P) controllers are used, followed by a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller where the selection among the various P and the PID controllers depends on the specific flight mode.

2) *Lateral forces control (purple block)*: Similarly to the previous control, this block is also a cascade control composed by a one P controller and a PID controller.

3) *Z control (blue block)*: Another cascade control with a P and a PID controllers.

Focusing on the Lateral forces control, while flying in manual this is done in open loop. However, while flying in autonomous mode the UAV can be controlled either in velocity or position using the odometry provided by relative localization from the perception module. Simultaneously the attitude control block operates at $ROLL = PITCH = 0$.

Fig. 11. Illustration of the contact between aerial robot and pipe. ((a) Roll over movement caused by landing gear contact with pipe; (b) Action to counteract rollover moment)

In the context of pipe landing, a mechanism has been developed to mitigate potential instability scenarios, Fig. 11, that could result in tipping moments in the UAV therefore. It

consists in an pre-configured roll threshold that, if exceeded during a landing, triggers a force of the same magnitude and direction as the detected roll.

C. Flight Manager

The incorporation of UAVs into pipeline inspection processes presents a complex operational framework, which must be carefully designed. There must be both modules in charge of the safety of the operation, i.e. that no on-board sensor fails and that all algorithms run normally. In addition, there must be a module in charge of managing the status of the autonomous mission and the aircraft itself.

1) *Mission Manager*: This component ensures that everything runs smoothly in the execution of the mission. It shall assess the correct status of all the sub-components included and perform the data conversions necessary to execute the mission normally.

2) *Flight State Machine*: In Fig. 12 is shown the state machine diagram of the autonomous inspection process.

Fig. 12. Operation State Machine

This process of inspecting a pipe using an UAV commences with the "Finding Pipe" state, during which the system employs its operational sensors and navigation systems to systematically search for the previously selected pipe within the designated area. By scanning methodically, the UAV looks for visual cues or distinctive landmarks that match the pipe's characteristics. Upon successful identification, it locks onto the pipeline, transitioning to the "Preparing to Land" state. In this state, the UAV maneuvers to align with the pipe and hovers stably above the pipeline, maintaining a consistent distance waiting to land. Once is ready, the landing procedure is done in two states. The "Prelanding" state descends the system to a constant speed up to certain height from the pipe. After the "Prelanding" height is achieved, the UAV enters the "Landing" state where it descends slower with a higher precision until it reaches the pipe's surface and attaches to it.

If the pipe momentarily disappears from its field of vision, the State Machine triggers the "Pipe Lost" transition, initiating a search mode to reacquire the target again. Upon re-identification, it transitions back to the "Prepare to Land" state. The mission concludes in the "Inspection" state, deploying the inspection crawler and signifying successful completion.

After the inspection is complete, the UAV moves to the "Taking Off" state, adjusting its altitude and attitude for a safe ascent. And finally returns to the home point in the "Return to Home" state.

In the event of anomalies, the UAV triggers the "abort" transition, initiating emergency measures and transitioning to the "Wait" state where it awaits further instructions from the Ground Control Station (GCS) for a timely and safe response to unforeseen issues, ensuring mission integrity and UAV safety.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section includes an evaluation of the components of the aerial platform. Specifically, some of the components were evaluated independently as well as the complete integration of all of them with an analysis of an autonomous landing.

It should be noted that all processing will be performed on the aircraft's on-board computer, which is an Intel NUC 10 Performance NUC10i7FNKN.

Therefore, first of all, an analysis of the performance of the LiDAR-Inertial odometry used, as well as an analysis of its errors, is presented. After that, the performance of the pipe detector will be evaluated in a qualitative way and, finally, the full analysis of a complete autonomous landing.

A. GNSS-denied Localization Evaluation

A Leica Total Station TS60 was used to obtain the localization ground truth. This tool allows us to track a prism with millimetre precision. As this tool can only track one point, it is not possible to estimate the orientation of the prism, so only the estimated position and not the orientation can be compared and evaluated. In other words, only the ground truth of position is available. This prism was placed on one of the legs of the landing gear in order to avoid any occlusion between the device and the prism during the flight. In order to correctly evaluate the algorithms, both ground truth and LiDAR-Inertial odometry were transformed to the centre of the aircraft, which is defined as the base link. This is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Placement of the point from which the ground-truth will be obtained, the position of the 3d LiDAR and the centre of the aerial robot.

Fig. 14 shows a comparison of the position estimation against the GT, so that the executed trajectory can be understood.

In order to evaluate the odometry estimate, the evo package, [10], has been used. The comparison between odometries is made by calculating the absolute pose error (APE) and

Fig. 14. Trajectory comparison between estimation and ground-truth.

the relative pose error (RPE). The APE metric evaluates the global consistency of the estimated trajectory by comparing the absolute distances between the estimations and the ground truth.

Fig. 15 shows that the mean absolute error of the estimated odometry is around 20cm, which is globally small enough to navigate safely in a complex environment such as a refinery.

Fig. 15. Absolute Pose Error in the executed trajectory.

In the RPE metric, instead of a direct comparison of absolute poses, the relative pose error compares motions ("pose-deltas"). This metric gives insights about the local accuracy. Fig. 16 shows that the mean error is around 1cm, which can lead us to conclude that the odometry estimation is sufficiently consistent in the short term.

B. Pipe Detection Evaluation

Since it has not been possible to obtain a ground truth of the complete pipe for this work, this component is demon-

Fig. 16. Relative Pose Error in the executed trajectory.

strated qualitatively with a series of images of the detection of the pipeline during the landing process.

Fig. 17 shows the detection of the pipeline with the on-board sensors in three different phases of the autonomous mission: detection, alignment with the pipeline and landing on the pipeline. It can be seen how the estimation remains stable throughout this process.

Fig. 17. Pipe Detection During Landing Procedure.

C. Autonomous Landing Evaluation

Finally, Fig. 18 includes the information of a complete landing. It shows the odometry estimated by the GNSS-denied odometry, the detection of the pipe and the control commands sent to the autopilot. In addition, the change between states of the autonomous flight state machine is also shown. Between each state transition, the position of the aerial robot is stable, demonstrating that the operation is performed safely and smoothly.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work has presented an aerial platform capable of landing on pipes in a fully autonomous manner and navigating in GNSS-denied environments. In addition, after landing, it has the capacity to deploy a robot crawler with the ability of perform thickness measurements on the wall of the pipes. Both the hardware and software architecture of the aerial robot have been presented.

Fig. 18. Graph of the autonomous aerial robot landing. The change between states of the autonomous state machine can be observed and how the command mode changes accordingly. When the red graph starts is the point at which the target pipe starts to be detected.

Although the theoretical basis of the algorithms is consistent, the pipeline detection algorithm should be improved. This is because the LiDAR-based algorithm is dependent on the aircraft being aligned with the pipe to generate the best possible estimations.

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